

Influence of Staff Training and Motivation on Job Performance of Academic Librarians in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The job performances of librarians are judged through quality services. However, there has been a noticeable drop in performance in the quality of work. In order to boost the performance of librarians, the concept of training and motivation is known to be intertwined with job performance. Thus, this study examined the influence of staff training and motivation on the job performance of academic librarians in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design. The population comprised 172 librarians in the academic library of sixteen higher educational institutions. Total enumeration was used. A structured questionnaire was adapted, validated and used to collect data. The Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for the constructs ranged from 0.751 to 0.823. The response rate was 81%. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential (multiple regression) statistics. Findings revealed that staff training significantly influenced the job performance of librarians ($\beta = 0.204$, $t = 2.893$, $p < 0.05$), motivation significantly influence the job performance of librarians ($R^2 = 0.196$, $p < 0.05$), individually, extrinsic motivation significantly influence job performance of librarians ($\beta = 0.870$, $r = 0.279$, $t = 3.148$, $p < 0.05$) and intrinsic motivation significantly influence job performance of librarians ($\beta = 0.436$, $r = 0.244$, $t = 2.749$, $p < 0.05$). Staff training and motivation jointly and significantly influence the job performance of librarians ($R^2 = 0.190$, $p < 0.05$). Motivation is the most important factor that influences the job performance of librarians and training. The study recommended that libraries should incorporate activities and incentives that motivate librarians. Also, educational institutions need extensive training sessions and computer-based training skills enhancement.

Keywords: *Academic Library, Job Performance, Librarian, Motivation, Staff Training*

Introduction

In any organization, job performance measures the efficiency of staff's ability to work and to improve on this; the organization must always consider employee interest in their policies, welfare packages and how to improve their work capacities; this may either be in the form of training, motivation among others which may have a multiplier effect on job performance. According to Saka and Salman (2014), job performance refers to discharging statutory duties or

functions based on workers' specialization. The performances of statutory duties are geared towards attaining an organization's objectives. Thus, it is believed that all establishment aims at high job performance, without which the goal and objective of a such establishment cannot be realized. Individual performance is generally determined by training and motivation, among others.

Staff training is one of the most critical ingredients in providing quality services. Training improves efficiency and innovation of working among technically and socially competent staff in career development. There is a continual need for the process of staff development and training. Training should be designed to ensure efficient performance for the dual benefit of the library system and the users. Staff training should therefore be orientated towards the libraries' needs and services but should recognize the requirements of the individual staff member. According to Jackson in Asante and Alemna (2015), training is the process by which employees acquire capabilities to aid in the achievement of organizational goals, hence the need for training activity to help in the achievement of the goals of librarians which is the total satisfaction of the clients in libraries.

Hafiza, Shah, Jamsheed and Zaman (2011) classified motivational factors into intrinsic and extrinsic rewards. The intrinsic rewards include empowerment and autonomy, recognition and appreciation and challenging tasks. The extrinsic rewards are pay, bonuses, fringe benefits and promotions. Job performance is workers' perception, assessment or attitude towards their job based on the degree/extent of motivation received; hence, job performance is the direct product of motivation. Upev and Chorun (2015), in their study on the impact of motivation on performance in the university library, concluded that participation in decision-making, job security, challenging work assignment, monetary reward and job incentives were motivation tools for enhancing performance.

Asante and Alemna (2015) assess training and development issues in Polytechnic Libraries in Ghana, and they believe that Polytechnic libraries do not have training policies. They brought to light that the majority of the staff of Polytechnic libraries required skills in Information Communication Technology (ICT) to enable them to meet the changing needs of the profession. Yaya, Uzohue and Akintayo (2016) investigated the relationship between the motivation and performance of librarians in Nigerian public universities. The study revealed a significant relationship between the motivation and performance of librarians in public university libraries in Nigeria. Meanwhile, empirical studies on the composite impact of staff training and motivation on the job performance of librarians in tertiary institutions in the Ogun state have received less attention which called for further investigation.

Problem Statement

The library helps provide and solve the information needs of different users: students, lecturers and other researchers. This is done through the assistance of librarians at various levels. However, research and observation show that most times, users complain that librarians do not attend to their queries properly, which could be attributed to a lack of training and motivation, which as a result, affects their job performance. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the influence of staff training and motivation on the job performance of librarians in Ogun state academic libraries.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of job performance of librarians in Ogun state academic libraries?
2. To what extent is training provided to librarians in Ogun state academic libraries?
3. What is the level of motivation among librarians in Ogun state academic libraries?
4. How does motivation affect job performance of librarians in Ogun state academic libraries?
5. What is the influence of staff training on job performance of librarians in Ogun state academic libraries?
6. What is the combined influence of staff training and motivation on the job performance of librarians in Ogun state academic libraries?

Methodology

The study employed a survey research design. The population of this study comprises 172 librarians in the academic library of the sixteen higher educational institutions in Ogun State, Nigeria. The sample comprised librarians in higher educational institutions in Ogun State. Since the population (172) of the study is not much, there is no need for sampling. Therefore, a total enumeration was used to include all population members. The study used the researcher's developed questionnaire tagged: "*Influence of Staff Training, Motivation and Job Performance of Academic Librarians Questionnaire (ISTMJPALQ)*". The questionnaire requests responses on a four (4) – point Likert Scale format. The initial drafts of the questionnaire were subjected to face validity by three experts from Information Resources Management Department. In order to ensure the reliability of the instrument, thirty (30) copies of the questionnaire were distributed among 30 librarians at Lagos State University, and Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument. The research instrument was valid and adjudged reliable because the individual variable Cronbach's alpha coefficient ranges from 0.752 to 0.823 for both the independent variable (Training and Motivation) and the dependent variable of job performance. Copies of the questionnaire were retrieved from the respondents after administration. The researcher spent four weeks in the field collecting the data from the respondents. Frequency counts and percentages were used for analyzing the data that were obtained from the questionnaire administered. Mean and standard deviation was used for analyzing the research questions. Regression analysis was used to test the study hypotheses.

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion of Findings

Analysis of Demographic characteristics

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

	Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	63	45.3
	Female	76	54.7
Age	Below 30 years	14	10.1
	30 – 40 years	61	43.9
	41 – 50 years	52	37.4
	51 years and above	12	8.6
Highest Educational	BLIS/B.Sc/B.Ed	47	33.8

Qualification	MLIS/M.Sc/M.ED	82	59.0
	PhD	10	7.2
Working Experience	Below 5 years	20	14.4
	5 – 10 years	72	51.8
	11 – 15 year	36	25.9
	16 years and above	11	7.9
	Assistant Librarian	28	20.1
Level/Position	Librarian II	31	22.3
	Librarian I	31	22.3
	Senior Librarian	28	20.1
	Principal Librarian	11	8.0
	Deputy Librarian	5	3.6
Total	University Librarian	5	3.6
		139	100

Table 1 indicates that participants were mostly females (54.7%), while their male counterparts had 45.3% representation in the study. This suggests that more than half of the librarians in Ogun State academic libraries were females. In addition, many of the participants were between the ages of 30 and 40 years (43.9%), followed by librarians who were between the ages of 41 of 50 years (37.4%), while older participants (51 years and above, 8.6%) were the least represented in the study. This depicts that many librarians in Ogun State were either close to their mid-life ages or were already in their mid-life ages.

Majority of the librarians had MLIS/M.Sc/M.ED (59%), followed by those who had BLIS/B.Sc/B.Ed (33.8%), while few had PhDs (7.2%). This implies that the librarians were educated, hence would have the necessary skills to execute their job roles as librarians. Furthermore, more than half of the librarians had between 5 to 10 years of working experience (51.8%), followed by a quarter of librarians with 11 to 15 years of working experience (25.9%). However, only a few respondents had below 5 years (14.4%) and 16 years above of working experience (7.9%). This depicts that most of the librarians in academic libraries in Ogun State have had the adequate, requisite working experience to function properly as librarians. Lastly, these librarians had diverse levels/positions, which ranged from Assitant Librarian (20.1%), Librarian II (22.3%) to Deputy Librarian (3.6%) and University Librarian (3.6%).

There were more respondents from the Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta. (18.7%) than other academic libraries in Ogun State. Furthermore, Covenant University, Idiroko Road. Ota. Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro and Olabisi Onabanjo University, and Ago-Iwoye libraries had the same proportion of representation (10.1%). However, Abraham Adesanya Polytechnic Ijebu-Igbo., All-Over Polytechnic, Sango-Ota, Gateway Polytechnic, Saapade., McPherson University Seriki-Sotayo and Tai Solarin College of Education, Omu had the lowest representation of participants in this study (2.2%).

Findings and Discussion of Results

Research Question One: What is the level of job performance of librarians in Ogun State academic libraries?

Table 2: Librarians' Level of Job Performance in Ogun State

Items	VH	H	P	VP	\bar{x}	SD	AM

	4	3	2	F			
	F	F	F		(%)		
	(%)	(%)	(%)				
Team Work							
My level of engagement is	35 (25.2)	104 (74.8)	-	-	3.25	0.44	
My level of working with fellow colleagues is	10 (7.2)	127 (91.4)	2 (1.4)	-	3.19	0.43	
My level of assistance in team activity is	29 (20.9)	108 (77.7)	2 (1.4)	-	3.06	0.29	
							Average Mean
							3.17
Quality of Work							
The quality of information and attention I give is	54 (38.8)	84 (60.4)	1 (0.7)	-	3.38	0.50	
The level I employ the right knowledge/competency to work is	31 (22.3)	103 (74.1)	5 (3.6)	-	3.23	0.44	
The accuracy with which I perform my work is	33 (23.7)	105 (75.5)	1 (0.7)		3.19	0.48	
							Average Mean
							3.27

Quantity of Work

The number of duties I complete every day is	21 (15.1)	116 (83.5)	2 (1.4)		3.32	0.47	Average Mean 3.25
The volume and number of assistance I render to patrons seeking information in the library is	44 (31.7)	95 (68.3)	-	-	3.30	0.51	
The extent I accomplished tasks daily is	45 (32.4)	91 (65.5)	3 (2.2)	-	3.14	0.38	
Efficiency at Work							
My speed and efficiency is	79 (56.8)	56 (40.3)	4 (2.9)	-	3.54	0.56	Average Mean 3.36
My skill of supervision is	52 (37.4)	86 (61.9)	1 (0.7)		3.37	0.50	
The extent I keep to standards and ethics is	30 (21.6)	103 (74.1)	6 (4.3)	-	3.17	0.48	
Communication at Work							
The level of my human relations is	47 (33.8)	92 (66.2)	-	-	3.34	0.47	Average Mean 3.26
The level I share information is	35 (25.2)	98 (70.5)	6 (4.3)	-	3.23	0.52	
My effectiveness in command of language/ communication is	38 (27.3)	95 (68.3)	6 (4.3)	-	3.21	0.50	
Average Weighted Mean					3.26	0.45	

KEY: VH=Very High, H=High, P=Poor, VP=Very Poor *Decision Rule; if mean is 1 to 1.49=Very Low; 1.5 to 2.49=Low; 2.5 to 3.49=High; 3.5 to 4= Very High**

Table 2 shows that the level of job performance of librarians in Ogun State academic libraries was high (\bar{x} =3.26). The parameters of measurement indicate that the level of job performance in terms of Team Work (\bar{x} =3.17), Quality of Work (\bar{x} =3.27), Quantity of Work (\bar{x} =3.25), Efficiency at Work (\bar{x} =3.36) and Communication at Work (\bar{x} =3.26) were high. This implies that the level of job performance of librarians in Ogun State academic libraries was generally high and specifically good in respect of Team Work, Quality of Work, Quantity of Work, efficiency at Work and Communication at Work.

Research Question Two: To what extent is training available to librarians in Ogun State academic libraries?

Table 3: Extent to which Training is Available to Librarians in Ogun State

Items	VLAEX	LATEX	LOEX	VLOEX	\bar{x}	SD
	4	3	2	1		
	F	F	F	F		
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)		
Conference is organized for librarians.	1 (0.7)	113 (81.3)	19 (13.7)	6 (4.3)	2.78	0.52
Computer-based training is frequently organized for librarians.	9 (6.5)	32 (23)	96 (69.1)	2 (1.4)	2.35	0.62
Workshop is frequently organized for librarians.	10 (7.2)	34 (24.5)	89 (64)	6 (4.3)	2.35	0.68
Seminars are organized for librarians	4 (2.9)	32 (23)	101 (72.7)	2 (1.4)	2.27	0.54
Self-instruction is recognized among librarians.	1 (07)	28 (20.1)	108 (77.7)	2 (1.4)	2.20	0.45
Coaching is frequently organized for librarians.	4 (2.9)	23 (16.5)	108 (77.7)	4 (2.9)	2.19	0.52
There is a presence of job rotation among librarians.	4 (2.9)	16 (11.5)	115 (82.7)	4 (2.9)	2.14	0.49
Classroom courses are among training for librarians.	6 (4.3)	11 (7.9)	118 (84.9)	4 (2.9)	2.14	0.51
Average Weighted Mean					2.30	0.54

KEY: VLAEX=Very Large Extent, LAEX=Large Extent, LOEX=Low Extent, VLOEX=Very Low Extent***Decision Rule; if mean is 1 to 1.49=Very Low Extent; 1.5 to 2.49 = Low Extent; 2.5 to 3.49 = Large Extent; 3.5 to 4= Very Large Extent

Table 3 shows that a low extent of training was available to librarians in Ogun State academic libraries (\bar{x} =2.30). Items on the scale, however, showed that: conferences were frequently organized for librarians to a large extent (\bar{x} =2.78), while other items indicate that training such as computer-based training, workshop, seminars, self-instruction, coaching, job rotation and classroom courses were available to librarians to a low extent. These imply that conference attendance was available to librarians more in Ogun State academic libraries, while other training avenues such as a workshop, seminars, self-instruction, coaching, job rotation and classroom courses were available to librarians to a low extent.

Research Question Three: What is the level of motivation among librarians in Ogun State academic libraries?

Table 4: Level of Motivation among Librarians in Ogun State

Items	VHL	HL	LL	VLL	\bar{x}	SD	AM
	4	3	2	1			
	F	F	F	F			
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)			
Extrinsic							
Condition of training is	6 (4.3)	94 (67.6)	35 (25.2)	4 (2.9)	2.73	0.58	Average Mean 2.49
The level of job enrichment is	5 (3.6)	84 (60.4)	50 (36)	-	2.68	0.54	
The level of job security is	9 (6.5)	60 (43.2)	70 (50.4)	-	2.56	0.62	
The condition of staff welfare is	1 (0.7)	49 (35.3)	83 (59.7)	6 (4.3)	2.32	0.57	
The level of career development is	-	49 (35.3)	85 (61.2)	5 (3.6)	2.32	0.54	
Payment of reasonable salaries and wages are	1 (0.7)	47 (33.8)	85 (61.2)	6 (4.3)	2.31	0.56	
Intrinsic							
My work experience enhances my effective job performance.	8 (5.8)	80 (57.6)	51 (36.7)	-	2.69	0.58	Average Mean 2.41
The system of job recognition in place in my organization motivates me to improve on the quality of work.	4 (2.9)	67 (48.2)	68 (48.9)	-	2.54	0.56	
There are opportunities for advancement for me in my organization	6 (4.3)	50 (36)	83 (59.7)	-	2.45	0.58	
I am inspired to pursue further studies because it enables me to face challenging task	20 (14.4)	4 (2.9)	113 (81.3)	2 (1.4)	2.30	0.73	
Higher responsibility given to me promotes my level of job performance	2 (1.4)	34 (24.5)	101 (72.7)	2 (1.4)	2.26	0.50	
I leveraged on the benefit of teamwork and delegation to excel at tasks.	12 (8.6)	10 (7.2)	115 (82.7)	2 (1.4)	2.23	0.62	
Average Weighted Mean					2.45	0.58	

KEY: VHL=Very High Level, HL=High Level, LL=Low Level, VLL=Very Low Level*Decision Rule; if mean is 1 to 1.49=Very Low Level; 1.5 to 2.49 = Low Level; 2.5 to 3.49 = High Level; 3.5 to 4= Very High Level**

Table 4 indicates that the motivation level among librarians in Ogun State academic libraries was generally low (\bar{x} =2.45). The dimensions of measurement depict that both extrinsic (\bar{x} =2.49) and intrinsic (\bar{x} =2.41) motivation among librarians in Ogun State academic libraries was low. Conversely, extrinsic motivation in terms of the condition of training (\bar{x} =2.73), level of job enrichment (\bar{x} =2.68) and level of job security (\bar{x} =2.56) was high; while it was low in terms of staff welfare (\bar{x} =2.32), career development (\bar{x} =2.32) and payment of reasonable salaries and wages (\bar{x} =2.31). In addition, intrinsic motivation was high in terms of work experience (\bar{x} =2.69) and job recognition (\bar{x} =2.54), while intrinsic motivation was low in respect of opportunities for advancement (\bar{x} =2.45), the pursuit of further studies (\bar{x} =2.30), higher responsibility (\bar{x} =2.26) and the benefit of teamwork and delegation (\bar{x} =2.23) were low among librarians in Ogun State academic libraries.

Research Question Four: What are the challenges to the job performance of librarians in academic libraries?

Figure 1: Challenges of Job Performance among Librarians in Ogun State

Figure. 4.2 indicate that the challenge mostly faced by librarians in academic libraries in Ogun State in terms of job performance was poor or lack of motivation (84.2%), many librarians perceived poor workplace relationships (41%), burnout/stress (38.5%), ineffective leadership (28.1%) and inadequate tools (21.6%) as factors that reduce librarian's job performance. Fewer librarians perceived work-life balance (14.4%) and complex performance management (11.5%) as challenges that adversely affect job performance. This suggests that poor or lack of motivation mostly affected librarian's job performance, followed by poor workplace relationships, burnout/stress, ineffective leadership and inadequate tools.

Summary and Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the influence of staff training and motivation on the job performance of librarians in Ogun State. The following summary and discussion were arrived at.

- 1 The level of job performance among Librarians in academic libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria, was high.
- 2 The level of motivation among Librarians in Academic Libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria, was low.
- 3 The extent of staff training among Librarians in Academic Libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria, was low.
- 4 The key challenges of job performance were poor motivation, burnout/stress and ineffective leadership.

Conclusion

The study reestablished that training and motivation influence employees' performance and service delivery. The absence of motivation in libraries, to a great extent, was responsible for some quality lapses in areas where the role of librarian extends to providing avenues for quality information and provisions of relevant information resources for research and decision-making. It can be deduced further from the responses that apart from personal reasons and work habits, the pay condition falls short of energizing and stimulating librarians to go beyond their required duty to satisfy patrons. Furthermore, lack of adequate training was the root cause of noticeable performance drops in the areas of teamwork, communication, efficiency and quality of service among librarians. Nowhere is the effect of training significantly more than in communication and ICT. It was observed that librarians' IT skills are falling behind the optimal level, making it difficult to meet the needs of ICT-savvy patrons. It is expected that training through seminars, conferences, and workshops should be organized to equip librarians with communication skills, ICT as well as hands-on skills.

Generally, the study emphasized that poor motivation and inadequate training were major causes of performance problems among librarians. However, equally important is the effect of inadequate work tools, burnout/stress, ineffective leadership, poor workplace relationships as well as work-life balance. The duo of welfare and training factors, if not well attended to with the diligence they deserve, will result in huge turnovers or militated against the performance of librarians in academic libraries in Ogun State. In view of this, the researcher concludes that training such as on-the-job training, workshop, conferences, seminars and motivational activities like adequate salaries and wages, regular promotions, career development, recognition of workers and improved conditions of service will positively influence librarian job performances in academic libraries in Ogun State.

Recommendations

This study offers the following recommendations:

1. Librarians need to be directed by the Institution management to practical training that will immediately impact on their jobs.

2. Different performance measures such as teamwork, communication and efficiency should be made into a measurable goal in the library by the University Librarian and head of the department of each section.
3. More importantly, educational institutions must expose their librarians to extensive training sessions such as workshops, seminars, classroom courses, self-instruction, conferences and computer-based training skills enhancement to serve the immediate needs of librarians.

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